

ARCHITECTURE AND HISTORICAL-CULTURAL SIGNIFICANCE OF THE ISHAN KALA COMPLEX OF THE 18TH-19TH CENTURIES IN THE TERRITORY OF KARAKALPAKSTAN

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Abstract: The current state of the Ishon-Kala architectural monument in Karakalpakstan, dating back to the 18th-19th centuries, its place in history and architecture, and aspects related to Sufism. Familiarization with the functions performed by the Ishon-Kala monument in its time and its current state.

Key words: mosque, madrasa, residence, architecture, monument, restoration, Sufism, pakhsa, fortress, pilgrimage tourism.

Karakalpakstan has long been known as a region rich in historical monuments. Various cities, fortresses, religious and cultural centers have been formed here since ancient times. Over the past centuries, some monuments have been well preserved, while others have been completely lost due to natural conditions and human factors. The 18th-19th and 20th centuries were a period when many fortresses, mosques, madrasas, and khanqahs were built in this region, some of which still exist today and testify to the rich historical memory of our people.

Among the architectural monuments of this period are the Karakum Ishon, Suyin Ishon, Abdikerim Akhun, Ayimbet Ishon, Kulamet Akhun Madrasah, Khan Mosque, Tas Madrasah, Abdikadir Eshon Madrasah, Abdukarim Akhun Madrasah, Qirantaw, Eshim Akhun, Abdikhalyk Ishon Madrasah, Nurulla Akhun Madrasah, and many others. All of them played important roles in the religious, educational, social, and cultural life of their time.

Among these monuments, the "Ishon Kala" complex holds a special place. This monument, built in the 18th-19th centuries in the Kegeyli district, is made of ordinary clay, simple in appearance, but of immeasurable historical and religious significance. The monument was closely connected with Sufi activity and functioned as one of the important centers in the spiritual life of the people. Even today, "Ishon Kala" is valued as an important source for studying the rich cultural heritage of Karakalpakstan. The "Ishan Kala" complex, located in the Kegeyli district of Karakalpakstan, is a vivid example of the architectural heritage of the 18th-19th centuries. The architectural traditions of Khorezm and Bukhara are noticeably reflected in its construction. This process is explained by the fact that local youth studied in these cities at that time and, upon returning

to their homeland, applied their knowledge in practice. Initially, the fortress was established as a religious and educational center, where about fifty students could study. There are open and closed gardens around it, which enhance the attractiveness of the complex.

The complex occupies a large area and is surrounded by high and thick walls. The foundation of the walls was reinforced with layers of wood and reeds, and the main building material was adobe. The castle walls contained bouquets of flowers, which, along with strengthening the walls, also performed an aesthetic function. The main gate was distinguished by its height and patterns.

The carved decorations on it are a vivid expression of the national art of that time.

The overall layout of the castle is complex, containing more than fifteen cells. These cells served as dormitories for students. The two-domed madrasah, located next to the fortress mosque, was one of the main centers of religious education. The complex has acquired significance not only as an educational center but also as a shopping center. The appearance of the fortress gates and architectural elements is very similar to the monuments of that period in the cities of Khorezm and Bukhara.

Although the historical significance of "Ishan Kala" is great, today most of the monument is in ruins. Its walls were destroyed due to natural disasters, rain and snow waters, and human factors. Currently, some parts have been turned into a cemetery. Nevertheless, the complex is recognized as one of the most important historical monuments of Karakalpakstan, and in the future, the issues of its restoration, preservation, and attraction to tourism remain relevant.

The issues of in-depth study of the current state of historical monuments and their preservation are of current importance. It is necessary to restore monuments in need of restoration, develop scientifically based projects, and restore them based on modern technologies. This is an important condition not only for the preservation of historical heritage, but also for its healthy transmission to future generations. The careful preservation and restoration of monuments will serve to increase their tourism potential and attract more tourists visiting our country.

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